

A Preliminary Study on the Extent of Entomophagy in the Mbieri Community, Mbaitolu Local Government Area of Imo State

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ABSTRACT:

The extent of entomophagy was established amongst randomly chosen indigenes of the Mbieri community in Mbaitoli Local Government Area, Nigeria. In the villages of Mbieri, the community with the greatest prevalence of insect eating and consumption was Umudagu, with a great liking for edible insects as part of their diet. Structured questionnaire technique was used to collect data. It was discovered that there was great consumption of insects, with adult males (51.4%) leading in terms of insect consumption. There was no significant difference in the rate of insect consumption between children (33.0%) and adults (67.0%) ($p > 0.05$). Though both the larvae and adults of insects (61.8% and 27.7%, respectively) were consumed, the larvae were the most common. Only 92.7% of respondents did not suffer any side effects, while 7.3% of them did not know what to expect. Four orders of insects with thirteen different species, namely Orthoptera, Lepidoptera, Isoptera, and Coleoptera were identified, with termites (27.9%), caterpillars (25.4%), and beetles (23.5%) consumed more than others. Frying was the most common method of insect preparation (55.4%) compared to roasting (27.5%) ($p < 0.05$). Edible insects were available in the open market, mostly as larvae (62.4%) and imago (27.6%). The implications of these findings on food security and cultural dietary practices were discussed.

Keywords: Entomophagy, Orthoptera, Lepidoptera, Isoptera, Mbieri, Imo State

INTRODUCTION:

Insects have been discovered to be very useful in providing solutions to the problems associated with food security due to their ability to serve as foods, which practice is called entomophagy. Insects contain a lot of nutrients such as proteins, fat, vitamins, and minerals which can replace nutrients obtained from livestock foods. According to some researchers, over two billion people in the world feed on insects and over 2,100 edible species have been identified (FAO, 2021). However, the consumption of insect is common among people in places where the insects are found in plenty and they are socially accepted. With the increasing number of people and pressure on the environment by the use of conventional agricultural methods, entomophagy is becoming very popular as the insects can serve as a good source of food. There are many edible insects such as termites, Crickets, caterpillars, Grubs and Locusts. The use of entomophagous insects in Nigeria is very widespread (Okore et al., 2014; Ebenebe and Okpoko, 2015; Iwunze et al, 2026). The larvae of *Cirina forda* (Lepidoptera:

Saturnidae) and adult of *Zonocerus* species (Orthoptera: Pyrgomohidae) are consumed in parts of Nigeria (Ogunleye and Omotoso, 2005) as well as substitutes in food ratio for experimental Albino rat (Ogunleye and Edward, 2005). Winged reproductive termites, *Macrotermis* species locally known as 'akuebe' are prominent among edible insects in south eastern part of Nigeria where they serve as alternative source of protein (Ebenebe and Okpoko, 2015). Previous studies on termites have either centered on pest species or checklist on entomophagy. Hitherto no study is known to have associated edible insects with carriage of pathogens. Historically, entomophagy has been an integral part of many indigenous cultures, particularly in Africa, Asia, and Latin America. In these regions, insects have been consumed for centuries, not only as a source of nutrition but also as part of cultural and ritualistic practices. For example, in West Africa, certain insects like termites and caterpillars are considered delicacies and are often associated with specific cultural ceremonies (Dobermann and Swift, 2017). In Mexico, the consumption of

grasshoppers dates back to pre-Hispanic times and remains a popular culinary practice today. The cultural acceptance of entomophagy varies widely, with some societies embracing it as a norm, while others may view it with skepticism or as a practice limited to periods of food scarcity. However, recent shifts in global food culture have led to a renewed interest in entomophagy, particularly in the context of sustainable food systems (Durst and Hanboonsong, 2018). In rural communities such as Mbieri in Mbaitolu Local Government Area, Imo State, Nigeria, entomophagy plays a crucial role in ensuring food security and nutritional diversity. These communities often face challenges such as limited access to conventional protein sources due to economic constraints or geographic isolation. Insects, which are abundant and require minimal resources to harvest, provide an accessible and sustainable source of protein. The nutritional value of edible insects, such as caterpillars and palm weevil larvae, is well-documented, and their consumption can help alleviate malnutrition in protein-deficient areas (Akullo et al., 2018). In Mbieri, where traditional agricultural practices may not always meet the dietary needs of the population, entomophagy not only supplements the diet but also contributes to the community's resilience against food shortages and economic hardships.

Mbieri is a rural community located in Mbaitolu Local Government Area of Imo State, Nigeria. The community's economy is predominantly agrarian, with most residents engaged in subsistence farming. Crops such as cassava, yam, and maize are commonly cultivated, while small-scale livestock rearing, including poultry and goats, supplements the community's food supply. Despite its agricultural base, Mbieri faces several socio-economic challenges, including limited access to markets, poor infrastructure, and declining agricultural productivity due to soil degradation and changing climate patterns (Mbieri Research Study Group, 2024). In this context, entomophagy offers not only a reliable source of nutrition but also a potential income-generating activity, as insects can be harvested and sold in local markets (Ooninx and Finke, 2021). The practice of entomophagy in Mbieri therefore, is not only a dietary habit but also a critical aspect of the community's socio-economic strategy for sustainability and resilience. With the growing global interest in alternative protein sources to address the challenges of food security and environmental sustainability, this study can serve as a case example of how entomophagy can be effectively integrated into local food systems. The findings of this research may also inform policy development and interventions aimed at promoting entomophagy as a viable component of food security strategies in other similar rural communities. Moreover, documenting the practices and perceptions of entomophagy in Mbieri will contribute to the preservation

of indigenous knowledge and cultural heritage, which are often overlooked in modern agricultural and nutritional discourses.

Objectives

- To determine the prevalence of entomophagy in Mbieri community
- To identify edible insect species consumed
- To assess harvesting and preparation methods
- To evaluate cultural acceptance and marketability

Study Area:

This study was conducted in the Mbieri community within the Mbaitolu Local Government Area of Imo State, Nigeria. Mbieri comprises several villages, including Achi, Amankuta, Amaulu, Awo, Ebom, Eziome, Obazu, Obokwe, Ohohia, Ubakuru, Umuagwu, Umuahii, Umudagu, Umuduru, Umunjam, Umuneke, Umuobom, Umuomumu, and Umuonyeali. The community is divided into autonomous entities such as Amaike-Mbieri, Awo-Mbieri, Ezi-Mbieri, Ihitte Isi-Mbieri, Obazu Mbieri, Obi-Mbieri, and Umueze-Mbieri. Located in the tropical rainforest zone of southeastern Nigeria, Mbieri is characterized by a tropical climate, with subsistence agriculture and petty trading as the main occupations. The area's cultural practices include masquerades and annual yam festivals, and its diet predominantly features yam and cassava.

Ethical Clearance:

Ethical clearance was obtained from the relevant local authority and the community leaders before commencing the study. Informed consent was secured from all participants, ensuring that they understood the purpose of the study and their right to withdraw at anytime. The study adhered to ethical guidelines for research involving human subjects, including maintaining confidentiality and anonymity.

Study Design:

A cross-sectional survey design was employed for this study. This design facilitated the collection of both quantitative and qualitative data on the practice of entomophagy within the Mbieri community. The study aimed to assess the prevalence and patterns of insect consumption, explore cultural attitudes, and determine the level of awareness about the nutritional value of edible insects.

Study Population:

The study population consisted of residents of Mbieri aged 11 years and older, who were capable of providing informed responses. A total of 200 participants from various villages within the community were randomly selected. The selection process aimed to ensure a

representative sample that reflects the diverse demographics of Mbieri.

Data Collection:

Data were collected using structured questionnaires distributed to the selected participants. The questionnaires included sections on the types of edible insects, their consumption patterns, knowledge of their nutritional value, and cultural significance. Group discussions were also held to gain deeper insights into cultural attitudes and practices related to entomophagy. The questionnaires were administered over a period of three months, allowing flexibility to accommodate participants' schedules.

Data Analysis:

Data collected from the questionnaires were analyzed to determine the prevalence of insect consumption, types of insects consumed, and the level of awareness about their

nutritional benefits. The data were also examined to understand the cultural attitudes towards entomophagy. The analysis involved both quantitative methods, such as frequency distributions and cross-tabulations, and qualitative methods, including thematic analysis of focus group discussions.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Residents aged 11 years and above
- Individuals willing to participate

Exclusion Criteria:

- Visitors/non-residents
- Individuals unwilling to consent

Plate 1: Rhynchophorus phoenicis (Eruru)

Plate 2: Rhynchophorus phoenicis (Eruru)

Plate 3: *Bunaea alcinoe* (Egu) in a Bowl

Plate 4: Fried *Zonocerus variegatus* (grasshopper) and *Lepidoptera litoralia* (caterpillar)

Plate 5: *Macrotermes bellicosus* (Aku)

Plate 6: *Zonocerus species* (Locust)

Plate 7: *Gymnogryllus lucus* (Cricket)

Plate 8: *Anaphe venata* (Ololo)

RESULTS:

Table 1 shows Insect Consumption and effects of edible Insects on consumers. All the adults and children ate insects. Insects were culturally eaten by adults and children in the proportion; adult males (33.0%), adult females (34.0%) and children (33.0%) respectively (Table 2). This suggests that more of the adults ate insects than the children. However, the children were of the opinion

that they too liked the insects as much as the adults but they ate only what they were given. Efforts made to find out if insect-eating had adverse effects on consumers showed that 92.7% of those eating insects clearly said insects had no known bad effects on them (Table 3). About 7.3% of such insect consumers were not sure of any effect on them because they had not taken time to observe if there had been any such effects (like allergies).

Table 2 shows that thirteen insect species were eaten. Three (Nchom, Apa and Ntekuru) are yet to be known by the order they belong. The other ten belonged to four insect orders namely; Orthoptera (Crickets and Grasshoppers), Isoptera (Termites), Lepidoptera (Caterpillars of butterflies and Moths) and Coleoptera (Beetles) (Plates 1-8). Termites and caterpillars were abundant. It was reported that green, brown and dull-colored grasshoppers were tasty whereas the brightly colored species taste badly. The reproductive termites after their nuptial flights in their millions shed their wings and cluster near very-lit points of night: They were easily harvested for food by man and other insectivores. The soldiers were harvested from termite mounds with special long, grass leaves. These soldiers clung fast to the leaves possibly believed to be intruders to their mound; in defense of their territory. They were then removed into a container to be processed later as food/ snack. The relative proportions of the insects eaten were also shown in Table 5. Isopteran (termites), Lepidoptera (caterpillars) and Coleoptera (beetles) contributed to 27.9%, 25.4% and 23.5% of all insects eaten, i.e. these three order provided 76.8 of all the insects eaten. Table 3 shows how Edible Insects are served, mode of preparation and Choice of Stage of Development of Insects Consumed. The preferred mode of use is indicated. About 70.8% of insects were eaten as snacks, 24.2% was deliberately eaten as protein supplement and 5.1% was used as condiment especially when fermented or fried. Preferred mode of preparation of the insects before they are served on the table. Frying was by far the most favored (55.4%) mode of preparation followed by roasting (27.5%).

Choice of Stage of Development of Insects Consumed showed that eggs of insects were not sought after for consumption. It was however, noted that some female adult and processed insects contained eggs. The stages of development of insects most usually eaten were the larvae. About 61.8% of all reported cases of consumed insects were at this stage of development. This was followed by choice in human dish by the adults which consisted of 27.7% of insects consumed. Only of pupae were consumed. It was observed that even though a larger number of larvae were eaten, adult insects were preferred by many adult respondents. In answer to why this situation, it was gathered that larvae of most eaten insects clustered together. It was easy to harvest them when they were together than when they were adults and could fly. The pupae were more difficult to get because of their relatively inactive state. Table 4 shows the sources of Edible Insects and Who Hunt/Harvest Edible Insects. Sources of insects indicates that Insects are harvested mainly from fallen palm trees (33.2%) followed by green vegetation (29.4%), Ant hills (27.5%) and Soil (9.9%). On who hunts and harvest edible insects shows that 51.4% of insect harvesters were adult males; 22.1% were adult females, 13.9% were young boys while 12.5% were young girls. Table 5 shows Seasonality of harvest and stages of Edible insects sold in open market. The table revealed that some insects are seasonal was (52.7%) while all year round was (47.3%). Also Edible insects were sold in the open market as larvae (62.4%), adults (27.6%) and pupae (8.6%). The species marketed depended on those species that were available according to the time of the year.

Table 1. Insect consumption and effects of Edible Insects on consumers

Variables	Number of people	Percentage proportion %
Who eats them N =252		
Adult males	83	33.0
Adult females	86	34.0
Children	83	33.0
Effects N =179		
No effects after eating	166	92.7
Don't know	13	7.3

Note some people chose more than one option in the questionnaire

Table 2: Edible Insects orders eaten in Mbieri

Order	Common Name	Local name	No of people N=323	Proportion (%)
Orthoptera	Cricket Grasshopper	Ntori	2	0.6
		Ukpala	7	2.2
Isoptera	Termite	Aku	90	27.9
		Mkpu	19	5.9

Lepidoptera	Caterpillars	Egu	82	25.4
		Nwaolile	10	3.1
		Ololo	18	5.6
Coleoptera	Beetle	Eruru	76	23.5
		Akika	1	0.3
		Wiyi	1	0.3
		Apa	4	1.2
		Nchom	2	0.6
		Ntekuru	11	3.4

Note: Some people chose more than one option in the available questions

Table 3: How Edible Insects are served, mode of preparation and Choice of Stage of Development of Insects Consumed

Variables	Number of people	Percentage Proportion (%)
How they are eaten N=178		
Main dish	0	0.0
Snacks	126	70.8
Protein source	43	24.2
Condiment	9	5.1
Mode of preparation N = 204		
Raw	0	0.0
Roasted	56	27.5
Fried	113	55.4
Fermented	14	6.9
Cook with others	21	10.3
Forms of insects eaten N=220		
Eggs	0	0.0
Larvae	136	61.8
Pupae	23	10.5
Imago(Adult)	61	27.7

Note: Some people chose more than one option in the available questions

Table 4. Sources of Edible Insects and Who Hunt/Harvest Edible Insects

Variables	Number of people	Percentage Proportion (%)
Sources of insects N =313		
Green vegetation	92	29.4
Fallen Palm trees	104	33.2
Ant hills	86	27.5
Soil	31	9.9
Insect Harvesters N =280		
Adult males	144	51.4
Adult females	62	22.1
Young boys	39	13.9
Young girls	35	12.5

Note: Some people chose more than one option in the available questions.

Table 5: Seasonality of harvest and stages of Edible insects sold in open market

Variables	Number of people	Percentage Proportion (%)
Seasonality of harvest N =186		
Seasonal	98	52.7
All year round	88	47.3
Forms they marketed N =313		
Larvae	138	62.4
Pupae	19	8.6
Imago(Adults)	61	27.6

Note: Some people chose more than one option in the available questions.

DISCUSSION:

It was established that insect consumption is well accepted in Mbieri with both adult and children taking part. This is in tandem with what Amaechi et al. (2024) discovered; that insect consumption is common practice among people of all ages in Nigerian communities. It means that the practice of eating insects is integrated into peoples' lives. Similarly, Amaechi et al. (2024) found out that there is broad acceptability of eating edible insects. It means that the act of eating insects is culturally ingrained hence it is not restricted to particular age groups or social class. Also, 92.7% of respondents reported that there were no adverse consequences of consuming insects, whereas 7.3% were uncertain. The general positive attitude towards the consumption of edible insects has been confirmed in the findings of Amaechi et al. (2024). The studies have shown that eating insects is safe and healthy when properly prepared. Edible insects are a valuable source of proteins. The uncertainty that only 7.3% of respondents had could be attributed to insufficient awareness concerning the impact of insect consumption on one's health. The study identifies that insects from the orders Orthoptera, Isoptera, Lepidoptera, and Coleoptera are consumed, with termites and caterpillars being the most prevalent. This observation is consistent with Amaechi et al. (2024), which reported similar preferences for these insect orders in Nigerian diets. Both studies highlight the significance of termites and caterpillars due to their nutritional value and availability. Amaechi et al. (2024) also noted that termites and caterpillars were commonly consumed in various Nigerian communities, reinforcing the findings from Mbieri.

In Mbieri, insects were predominantly served as snacks (70.8%), with a smaller percentage used as a protein supplement (24.2%) or condiment (5.1%). This aligns with the observations of Amaechi et al. (2010), which found that insects were commonly consumed as snacks or included in meals as a protein source. They also noted that insects were often enjoyed as snacks in Nigerian diets, supporting the findings from Mbieri. The preference for consuming insects as snacks in both studies highlights their role as a versatile food source in traditional diets. In

Mbieri, frying (55.4%) is the most favored method of preparing insects, followed by roasting (27.5%). This preference for frying aligns with the findings of Amaechi et al. (2024), which also identified frying as a popular preparation method due to its ability to enhance flavor and texture. Amaechi et al. (2024) observed that frying and roasting are commonly used to improve the palatability of insects, similar to the Mbieri study. The lesser use of fermentation and cooking with other ingredients in Mbieri reflects regional culinary practices and preferences, as also noted by Amaechi et al. (2024). The preference for larvae (61.8%) over adults (27.7%) and pupae (10.5%) in Mbieri aligns with findings from Amaechi et al. (2024), which also noted a strong preference for larvae due to their ease of collection and processing. Amaechi et al. (2024) found that larvae were commonly consumed due to their abundance and the simplicity of harvesting them compared to more mobile adult insects. This preference for larvae in both studies highlights the practical aspects of harvesting and consumption, where larvae are more accessible and less challenging to manage than adults or pupae. Insects in Mbieri were harvested from sources such as palm trees (33.2%), green vegetation (29.4%), ant hills (27.5%), and soil (9.9%). The study also notes that some insects are seasonal (52.7%), while others are available year-round (47.3%). This seasonal variation is consistent with Amaechi et al. (2024), which reported that insect availability can vary based on environmental conditions and seasonal factors. Amaechi et al. (2024) also highlighted the importance of diverse harvesting sources and the impact of seasonality on insect availability, reflecting the findings from Mbieri.

The study indicated that adult males (51.4%) were the primary insect harvesters, followed by adult females (22.1%), young boys (13.9%), and young girls (12.5%). This distribution of harvesting roles is consistent with Amaechi et al. (2024), which reported similar patterns in Nigeria, where men and boys were more involved in insect collection. Amaechi et al. (2024) observed that harvesting is often a communal activity involving various family members, reflecting the findings from Mbieri. The predominance of adult males in

harvesting roles in both studies underscores traditional labor divisions and highlights the importance of communal effort in insect collection. In the open market, edible insects in Mbieri are mainly sold as larvae (62.4%), followed by adults (27.6%) and pupae (8.6%). This distribution of insect stages for sale is consistent with Amaechi et al. (2024), which observed that larvae are often preferred due to their availability and ease of processing. Market trade of edible insects was found to be influenced by seasonal availability and consumer demand. The preference for larvae in both studies highlights their economic and practical advantages in the market.

CONCLUSION:

The study have underscore the cultural significance, health benefits, and market dynamics of insect consumption, while also identifying areas for improvement in knowledge, pest management, and food safety. The comparative analysis reinforces the importance of understanding local practices and integrating findings into broader discussions on entomophagy and sustainable food systems.

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The authors received no specific funding for this study.

Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Data Availability Statement:

Data are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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